

2024 SMD Data Repositories Workshop Retrospective Survey (Responses)

Timestamp	How did you attend the Open Source Science Data Repositories Workshop?	On a scale of 1 to 5 how would you rate the workshop overall?	Would you be interested in having this type of workshop on a regular cadence? (Annually, twice a year, or similar):	In a few sentences, please describe the part(s) of the meeting you feel went best, why?	In a few sentences, please describe the part(s) of the meeting you feel could improve, how?	(Optional) Please use this space for additional comments if you feel they will be helpful to capture your event experience.
10/3/2024 6:24:20	Virtual	5	Yes			
10/3/2024 6:47:49	In-Person	5	Yes	Hearing what's happening across SMD, exploring cross division collaborations, building relationships across divisions. Reasonably good job representing remote users in the room.	A few speakers were too soft (too far away from the microphone), a few speakers were too loud (very close to the microphone without volume compensation), and some speakers walked away from the microphone and were hard to hear. Several speakers didn't respect their time limits and/or went off topic from what I expected.	Excellent job by the organizers. They should feel very satisfied with their work on this workshop.
10/3/2024 8:08:50	In-Person	5	Yes	Conversations were productive and generally positive; I think people have embraced the value of having these cross-SMD exchanges and are eager to break down siloes.	I was in person and thought everything was smooth. My main concern was whether the virtual participants were able to hear and participate enough to have a valuable experience. Hybrid meetings are hard!	Thank you for organizing this – it was a really great event and it's clear how much thought and effort the planning committee put into this.
10/3/2024 9:42:19	In-Person	5	Yes	The follow sessions went best because they engaged the community with topics of interest. Enabling Open Science: The Big Picture Poster Session and Lightning Talks Data Impact Metrics And Measurement Introductory talks on metadata quality session and Desirable Characteristics session Desirable Characteristics of Data Repositories for Federally Funded Research Levels of Service Recap and Next Steps	The length of the poster session and lightning talks could be increased	Thank you for the efforts of the organizers!
10/3/2024 9:50:54	In-Person	5	Yes	I think the activities on the first day went well and it was great that they were so interactive and gave folks a chance to give ideas on one topic and then go around and see what ideas on other topics people had (and then comment on those). It gave us a wide breath of what people were thinking.	I think the poster session overall was great, but in terms of physical location, it was a little cramped. It could've benefited from being a little more spaced out and it might have also been good to have a few more posters so that posters didn't get crowded.	
10/3/2024 10:42:28	In-Person	5	Yes	The sessions on day 2 were great! The amount of time for discussion was nicely balanced with some presentations for context setting. The long breaks between the sessions (with snacks) were also great to support some short networking.	Would like to have short (~10 min) presentations from each science division about their overall status and challenges for data archiving. These likely need to be focused on some set of questions all divisions answer.	Using post-it notes in person did not go well. It was sometimes impossible to read the handwriting and some of them blew away.
10/3/2024 10:46:08	In-Person	4	Yes	Networking and exchanging information and ideas with repositories in other divisions is useful in and of itself.	Any effort to define standard metadata across divisions should be use case driven, and I have yet to see the use cases. Sessions discussing this should start with use cases.	
10/3/2024 11:29:11	In-Person	2	Yes	The ecocycle exercise was the best part, as it introduced a new way of thinking about our portfolio	We should have meeting spaces where food and drink are allowed. It was incredibly frustrating to have the main meeting space prohibit food/drink.	While talking across SMD repositories is helpful, I think NASA is fundamentally wrong that cross-SMD integration/unification is needed. With apologies, no one wants or needs the Science Discovery Engine. The fraction of people who simultaneously want, say, biology data from the international space station and astrophysics data is vanishingly small. It is true that we can all think of some kind of use cases for cross-SMD science. But the number of people who, in practice, can "do" this kind of science is basically zero. NASA needs to recognize that science is "collaborative" because of the specificity and specialization of sub-fields. Most scientists will never re-train across a different domain, what they need is to find a collaborator. What would be most helpful for these SMD repository meetings is for NASA to *actually listen to what we need* and not invent their own vision for something that no actually wants or needs. Spend the time and money investing in the domain-specific repository centers, because that is where real science is happening and where real scientists do real work.
10/3/2024 11:51:12	Virtual	4	Yes	Hearing what all the other divisions are doing and their plans for handling upcoming requirements and trends.	Identification and clarification of specific, collaborative outcomes - have the workshop focus on one (maybe two, but probably just one each year) specific kind of development or joint activity across SMD themes where progress could be made during the meeting. Examples might include: What is the right level of cross-SMD metadata? Metadata ingest is hard, especially from scientists, so what shared tools can be developed to simplify or automate this collection? What kind of cloud-based capabilities can be leveraged across divisions? Can we create a compendium of tools scientists can use to meet SPD-41a requirements for open science.	

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10/3/2024 12:52:42	Virtual	3	Yes	Day 3's discussions went best, and I wish that those were mentioned first. I appreciated the overall summaries of each of the prior breakout sessions as well, and that was appropriately on the third day.	One specific piece is that I was not a fan of the Miro board. It was hard to navigate and it became frustrating when people accidentally moved pieces or didn't follow the instructions. Perhaps an alternative is using GoogleSlides (but NOT Jamboard!), PearDeck, or other option. I did appreciate the attempt to help make it more engaging for the virtual attendees, though!	Overall I appreciated the session as a virtual attendee, but it does make for a set of very long on-screen days (even though we can have our cameras off and stretch, it's just not quite the same). I unfortunately don't have a solution to remedy this. Typically in person, I feel energized at the end of each day, but I found myself so drained. The content delivered itself was great and I thought it was really cool to hear about other groups, what they do, how they do, what we have in common, and what is different.
10/3/2024 12:57:25	In-Person	5	Yes	The meeting brought together technical experts from all the divisions to discuss similar issues. The ability to discuss these topics in person was invaluable.	The duration and hours of the meeting worked very well. For future meetings it would be helpful to have QR codes of the schedule or the schedule sent out ahead of the meeting. Before the meeting began, I was asked in the survey whether I had anything I wanted to talk about. I said I would be glad to talk but didn't have a topic in mind, partly because I don't do well with such open-ended questions. It would have been better if the survey had mentioned the topics that the organizers had in mind to discuss at the meeting, in which case I would have had some ideas that I could have shared.	Overall this was a wonderful workshop. Kudos to all the organizers and people who put in the time to make this successful.
10/3/2024 13:00:15	Hybrid	4	Yes	The most beneficial aspect of this meeting is simply the opportunity to be the same room with NASA archiving colleagues and to have conversations about our common work. I wouldn't want to do this more than once per year, but I find it very valuable. The discussion sessions themselves turned out to be very helpful also. I especially appreciated the discussion of Levels of Service. The Minimum FAIR discussion was a bit mislabeled, but the topics that were discussed were also quite helpful.	Logistics: Location information was unclear, Webex information was hard to access, and posters needed more support. a) The Hameetman Auditorium is not a place you can find on a map. It is just a room. The building is the Cahill Center, but that was never mentioned in meeting materials. By contrast, the Hameetman Center is a different building on campus. My car from the airport mistakenly went to the Hameetman Center, and then I had to walk across campus to the right place. I casually mentioned this to only one person, who said they had made the same mistake. b) I was late to the beginning of the meeting, and thought I would call in via the Webex. However, the calendar item had so many email addresses in it that on my phone it was truncated before it mentioned the Webex link, and I could not find the Webex link in any other meeting materials. Solutions could have included 1) not open-copying every single attendee's email address, and/or 2) adding the Webex link to the meeting agenda. c) The poster boards had very few pushpins available. I used the four pushpins allotted to me to put up my poster, and then the wind blew my poster away and it was damaged. More pushpins from the beginning would have really helped.	
10/3/2024 13:00:26	In-Person	3	No	It was good to hear from other disciplines and have them describe the data/metadata that have to deal with.	The poster "lightning" session could have been organized more tightly. Some suggestions: limit the presenters to 1 slide and use a loud, audible alert to let them know when their time is up. These poster pops should be teasers for the posters and not full talks. Also, depending on the number of presenters, it might be good to split the presentations into 2 or more groups.	
10/3/2024 13:11:13	In-Person	5	Yes	Sessions had enough time for discussion and folks wanted to contribute their thoughts and opinion. There were clearly people who came to this workshop wanting to share with AND learn from other divisions	ask every session to be sure to have discussion lead to some actionable next steps and identify how/who to be responsible for moving the activities forward during the year	A different space would be better. Not having food or drink in most of the rooms was inconvenient. Big thank you to Caltech for donating snacks and coffee, but those who could not do caffeine or gluten were left with no choices and no food/drink close enough to ensure sustenance was possible during the meeting. Thank goodness for long lunches! The timing (pace) of the workshop was very good, both for conversation /interaction and for lunch to get food. Thanks for a great workshop! I look forward to the next one.
10/3/2024 14:01:42	In-Person	4	Yes	Brought NASA data repositories community together, served as a window into seeing what is done in very different fields and what their problems and commonalities are	Not enough time to discuss everything. I liked the idea of an overlapping 2.5/2.5 day software/data repositories workshop, while understanding that could leave some people very drained by the end of it.	I hope to attend again in the future!

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10/3/2024 18:36:59	In-Person	4	Yes	It was great to have groups from all of the Science Topics collaborating. The general overview of what each area is doing was also very insightful.	The working sessions seemed to either lack the focus or the time to complete something meaningful. Even when the goal was a small bite, we barely scratched the surface. Smaller and/or more focused groups might make better progress. More frequent meetings might also help.	This was the first time I had any interactions with groups outside of Earth Science. There are a lot of overlaps in the work we do for Data Repositories, and probably other areas as well. It seems to me that a structure similar to ESIP, but focused on NASA could be very beneficial. They have several open meetings for specific topics on a monthly basis along with forums for asynchronous collaboration.
10/3/2024 19:49:40	In-Person	3	No		Learning about approaches used in different disciplines	There did not seem to be a coherent "call-to-action;" or plan for implementation coming out of the meeting
10/8/2024 8:54:18	Virtual	5	Yes	I enjoyed the research data talks on day two. It was interesting to hear talks by other divisions.		I think placing some in-person attendees in some of the virtual sessions. My second metadata breakout only had one person, and a few others didn't have anyone.
10/8/2024 12:07:13	In-Person	4	Yes	I am biased toward metadata issues, so I feel that the metadata quality and standards sessions were the most important. I believe that the standards session was better, especially where metadata standards were the topic. However, more issues could have been addressed. See below.	I believe that metadata quality and governance is directly related to the availability and adherence to standards. Maybe metadata quality should be a subtopic under standards. In any case, in my opinion metadata standards should start at a conceptual level. For example, SMD might adopt and promote a standard for "defining vocabulary terms". This seems to represent a most basic way to promote "Interoperability" and "Reuse" by standardizing structure of the vocabularies for easier sharing. This also starts to address the two most obscure parts of the FAIR guidelines. ISO 11179 represents a comprehensive standard for this purpose that could be "watered down" into some best practices. (The schema allows a data element to be defined separate from its value domain. - e.g. The definition of image_start_time would be defined separately from its possible values, for example time formats conforming to ISO 8601.) ISO 11179 has also been used to capture and manage ontology and taxonomy content. In addition, a standard for multilevel governance scheme is essential for managing change to the standards caused by the evolving science disciplines and the evolution of the technology used for the implementation of the Information Systems. I apologize for using more than a few sentences.	Nothing else for now. :-)